

Concept Paper: Exploring the Key Factors Influencing Socially Responsible Investment Intentions and the Moderating Role of Perceived Financial Performance

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ABSTRACT

In the dynamic world of investment, there is a significant transition from solely chasing financial returns to a comprehensive approach that also weighs societal and environmental consequences. This change is evident in the rising trend of Socially Responsible Investment (SRI) strategies, which seamlessly blend financial goals with ethical and sustainable goals. As global challenges like climate change and social equity become more pressing, understanding the factors influencing individuals' SRI intentions becomes crucial. This concept paper explores the factors guiding individuals towards SRI, leveraging the Value-Belief-Norm (VBN) Theory. This theory explains the interrelation between personal values, beliefs, social norms, and pro-environmental actions, including SRI. The concept paper further innovates by introducing perceived financial

performance as a potential moderator in this relationship. With the surge of global SRI assets to a notable \$35.3 trillion, it's undeniable that investors are integrating their financial objectives with larger community expectations. This concept paper aims to offer a deeper understanding of how personal values, beliefs, and norms, when viewed through the lens of perceived financial performance, shape SRI intentions. The results will hold the potential to shape both scholarly insights and the decision-making of investors and policymakers in the domain of responsible investing.

Keywords— Socially Responsible Investments (SRIs), Value-Belief-Norm (VBN) Theory, Values, Beliefs, Norms, Perceived Financial Performance.

1. INTRODUCTION

In the rapidly changing world of investment, there has been a significant shift from solely pursuing financial gains to considering the broader impacts on society and the environment. This shift is exemplified by the increase in SRI strategies, where financial goals are linked to ethical and sustainable goals (Wieland, 2016). Given the complex challenges the global community faces, such as climate change, social equity, and corporate responsibility, understanding the factors that shape individuals' intentions towards SRI has become increasingly important (Jansson & Biel, 2020).

This concept paper aims to shed light on the various influential forces that lead individuals to make socially responsible investment choices. It specifically draws on the VBN Theory, which offers a comprehensive framework for understanding the relationships among personal values, beliefs, social norms, and intentions towards pro-environmental behaviours, including participation in SRI (Stern et al., 1999). Expanding on this foundation, we extend the VBN theory to explore how these factors collectively shape individuals' intentions to engage in SRI. According to the Global Sustainable Investment Alliance (GSIA), global sustainable investment assets reached an impressive \$35.3 trillion, representing a remarkable 15% increase in just two years (GSIA, 2022). This growth emphasizes the transformation of investment practices beyond a purely financial perspective, signalling a new

era where investors actively seek to align their financial endeavours with broader societal goals.

While the VBN framework provides a strong theoretical basis for understanding the dynamics of SRI intentions, this concept paper goes a step further. It proposes that the relationship between personal values, beliefs, norms, and SRI intentions may be influenced by a crucial but often overlooked factor—perceived financial performance. In an investment landscape that requires a balance between ethical aspirations and financial returns, individuals' perceptions of SRI's financial viability could significantly impact their intentions to participate in such endeavours (Stern et al., 1995).

By exploring the potential moderating role of perceived financial performance, this concept paper aims to provide new insights into the insightful connection between individuals' values, beliefs, norms, and SRI intentions. The findings of this investigation will have implications that go beyond theoretical scopes, influencing the strategic decisions of investors, financial institutions, and policymakers navigating the ever-evolving field of responsible investing.

2. LITERATURE REVIEW

2.1 Predictors of Value-Belief-Norm (VBN) Theory:

VBN theory is a useful framework for comprehending how personal values impact environmental behaviour (Tangen, 2020). According to Stern et al. (1999), individuals' personal values, particularly altruistic and biospheric values, have a significant influence on their attitudes towards pro-environmental

behaviours. Recent studies have demonstrated that these predictors can also be applied to understand investment behaviours, specifically in socially responsible investments (Smith et al., 2018).

2.2 Personal Values Aligned with Social and Environmental Concerns:

The increasing popularity of sustainable investments can be attributed to individuals' desire to align their personal values with social and environmental issues (Johnson & Schueth, 2007). This tendency often arises from a genuine concern for the well-being of society and the preservation of the environment. Clark et al., (2019) observed that investors are more likely to invest in socially responsible options when they perceive a congruence between their personal values and the core values of these investment choices.

2.3 Beliefs about the Impact of Socially Responsible Investments on Society and the Environment:

The decisions made by investors are greatly influenced by their belief systems. When investors hold the belief that their investments can have a positive impact on society and the environment, they tend to favour socially responsible investments (Harjoto & Laksmana, 2018). Baxter and Moles (2016) suggest that investors who strongly believe in the societal and environmental effects of their investments are more likely to stay committed to socially responsible portfolios.

2.4 Perceptions of Social Norms:

According to Jackson (2013), social norms, which refer to the expectations and accepted behaviours within a

society, have a substantial impact on investment decisions. When investors perceive socially responsible investing as a norm, they are more inclined to align their portfolios accordingly. In their study, Davis et al. (2017) discovered that in communities where sustainable investment was considered a common practice, individual investors demonstrated a greater interest in and prioritization of these types of investments.

2.5 Perceived Financial Performance

The notion that socially responsible investments may generate lower returns than traditional investments has long been a source of worry for investors (Renneboog et al., 2008). Nevertheless, a recent study conducted by Fernandez and Kölbl (2020) reveals that sustainable portfolios have the potential to perform just as well, if not better, than conventional portfolios. This change in perception regarding the financial performance of socially responsible investments has significantly contributed to the increased interest and participation of investors in this field.

2.6 Socially Responsible Investment Intentions:

The decision to invest responsibly is influenced by multiple factors, as explained earlier. The investor's intention to engage in socially responsible investments is determined by a combination of personal values, beliefs, perceptions of social norms, and perceived financial performance (Lee & Shin, 2010). Recent empirical research demonstrates that investors are motivated not only by financial gains but also by a desire to make significant contributions to society and the environment.

3. HYPOTHESES AND THE CONCEPTUAL FRAMEWORK

3.1 Values and Socially Responsible Investment Intentions

Values are enduring motivational goals that guide individuals' attitudes and behaviours. In the context of SRI, values play a significant role in shaping investment intentions. Han et al., (2021) found that individuals who prioritize values related to social justice, environmental stewardship, and ethical responsibility are more likely to express positive intentions toward SRI participation (Geraldine, & Ottemoesoe, 2022). This aligns with the fundamental premise of the VBN Theory, which suggests that personal values act as a foundation for shaping individuals' pro-environmental intentions. Therefore, it is proposed:

H1a: There is a relationship between individuals' personal values aligned with social and environmental concerns and their intentions to engage in socially responsible investing.

3.2 Beliefs and Socially Responsible Investment Intentions:

Beliefs play a significant role in influencing an individual's willingness to engage in a particular behaviour. In the context of Socially Responsible Investing, beliefs regarding the positive societal and environmental impacts of such investments can serve as a motivating factor for individuals to participate in SRI (Saci et al., 2022). Kaiser and Menkhoff (2014) found that individuals who perceive their SRI choices as contributing to positive changes are more likely to express their intentions to invest responsibly. This finding aligns with the emphasis of the VBN framework, which recognizes the influence of beliefs on shaping

behavioural intentions. Therefore, we propose:

H1b: There is a relationship between individuals' beliefs about the impact of socially responsible investments on society and the environment and individuals' intentions to engage in socially responsible investing.

3.3 Norms and Socially Responsible Investment Intentions:

Social norms have a significant impact on how individuals behave, including their intentions to engage in SRI. These norms can be divided into descriptive norms, which involve perceptions of what others are doing, and injunctive norms, which involve perceptions of what should be done (Geraldine, & Ottemoesoe, 2022). According to a study by Renee and Tangen (2020), individuals are more likely to participate in SRI when they feel pressure from their peers and social circles to do so. This finding supports the VBN Theory and highlights the crucial role that social norms play in shaping pro-environmental intentions. Based on this, we suggest:

H1c: There is a relationship between perceptions of social norms and individuals' intentions to engage in socially responsible investing.

3.4 Perceived Financial Performance and Its Moderating Role

The financial performance of SRI has a significant impact on investment decisions. According to Statman (2000), individuals' willingness to invest in SRI is often influenced by their expectations of financial returns. This aspect, which is not adequately addressed in the existing VBN paradigm, introduces an important consideration—the role of perceived financial performance. In SRI, the influence of individuals' values, beliefs,

and norms may vary depending on their perception of financial stability (Statman, 2000). Schueth (2003) suggests that even investors with strong ethical inclinations seek assurance regarding the financial viability of their choices. Additionally, Renneboog et al., (2008) discovered that while social and environmental factors significantly influence SRI decisions, the perceived financial health of these investments is equally crucial in shaping investor behaviour. By integrating these insights, it becomes evident that the assessment of financial returns plays a crucial role in moderating the relationship between individuals' core personal values and their intentions to engage in SRI. Thus, we can hypothesize:

H2a: The relationship between individuals' personal values and their intentions to engage in socially responsible investing is moderated by the perceived financial performance of such investments.

H2b: The relationship between individuals' beliefs and their intentions to engage in socially responsible investing is moderated by the perceived financial performance of such investments.

H2c: The relationship between individual's social norms and their intentions to engage in socially responsible investing is moderated by the perceived financial performance of such investments.

Figure 1. Conceptual Framework

4. THEORETICAL IMPLICATIONS

The anticipated outcomes of this study have the potential to provide valuable insights into the predictors of SRI and shed light on the role of perceived financial performance as a moderator. Based on the principles of the VBN Theory, we expect to discover significant connections between personal values, beliefs, and norms, and individuals' intentions towards SRI. Building upon previous research (Han et al., 2021; Renee & Tangen, 2020), we anticipate that individuals who prioritize values aligned with social and environmental concerns will demonstrate stronger intentions to engage in socially responsible investing.

Additionally, we hypothesize that perceived financial performance will play a moderating role in the relationship between influential factors and SRI intentions. As suggested by Statman (2000), positive perceptions of financial returns from SRI ventures could strengthen the link between individuals' intrinsic motivations and their intentions. The findings of this study will contribute to the growing body of knowledge in the field of SRI by clarifying how financial considerations interact with core motivational factors.

The implications of this study extend to the theoretical domain, enhancing our understanding of how personal values, beliefs, and norms collectively shape SRI intentions within the framework of the VBN Theory (Robiyanto et al., 2019). The identification of perceived financial performance as a moderating factor enriches the existing theoretical landscape and opens up opportunities for further exploration.

5. MANAGERIAL IMPLICATIONS

This study will provide valuable insights for professionals in the investment industry, financial advisors, and policymakers. It will shed light on the complex factors that influence individuals' decisions to engage in socially responsible investing. By understanding the impact of perceived financial performance, these stakeholders can develop strategies that align with investors' motivations and potentially increase participation in socially responsible investing. This understanding can promote more sustainable and responsible investment practices, ensuring that the financial sector adjusts its strategies to meet the changing mindset and preferences of today's investors.

1. CONCLUSION AND REFLECTIONS ON FURTHER RESEARCH

In conclusion, this concept paper presents a comprehensive exploration of the relationship between influential factors and SRI intentions. Grounded in the VBN Theory, this research aims to uncover the underlying psychological mechanisms that drive individuals' intentions to engage in SRI. By considering the moderating influence of perceived financial performance, this concept paper seeks to enhance our

understanding of how this factor interacts with personal values, beliefs, and norms, shaping decision-making processes. The anticipated findings have the potential to inform investment strategies, promote more sustainable financial practices, and contribute to the ongoing discourse on responsible investing.

Building on this foundation, future research can expand in several directions: further exploring unexplored predictors within the VBN theory that influence socially responsible investments; examining the evolution and adaptability of personal values in different socio-economic contexts; investigating the formation and validation of investment beliefs in light of real-world societal and environmental outcomes; and understanding new implications of normative influences across diverse cultural contexts. Additionally, it is crucial to reassess investor perceptions of the financial performance of socially responsible investments, particularly in an ever-evolving global financial landscape. Holistic models that involve a broader range of psychological, economic, and socio-cultural variables could provide a more comprehensive understanding of investor intentions. The moderating role of perceived financial performance in these models warrants further investigation, and there may be a potential in examining other variables, such as perceived societal and financial risks. Comparative cross-cultural studies could shed light on how deeply established cultural values shape investment intentions.

Lastly, insights from the extensive body of literature have implications for financial education, highlighting the importance of cultivating a new

generation of investors who align financial goals with societal and environmental well-being. Incorporating these diverse perspectives could potentially lead to a thorough comprehension of the investment environment in future academic investigations.

2. REFERENCES

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